

Finding your way in the FAIR landscape

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List of frequent acronyms

CDR: ELIXIR Core Data Resource
CTS: CoreTrustSeal
DANS: Data Archiving and Network Services
DMP: Data Management Plan
DSCC: Data Stewardship Competence Centers
DSW: Data Stewardship Wizard
DTL: Dutch Techcenter for Life Sciences
EDD: ELIXIR Deposition Database
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
IN: Implementation Network (GO FAIR)
KSA: Knowledge, Skills and Abilities
RDA: Research Data Alliance
RDA IG: Research Data Alliance Interest Group
RDM: Research Data Management

Since the publication of the FAIR principles by Wilkinson *et al.* in 2016, there has been an increase of FAIR-related projects and organizations with names containing this acronym. FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reproducible. It represents a collection of fifteen guiding principles and practices that initially targeted datasets. It has since then been extended to the services and infrastructure acting on these Digital Objects. It is often difficult and confusing to understand the activities and responsibilities of each initiative, as well as how they all relate to each other and collaborate to create a FAIR ecosystem.

This document intends to answer these questions, using a network of these initiatives, organizations and outputs, as a map to guide its audience in the FAIR landscape (Figure 1). The accompanying text provides more details on each of these elements with information collected and presented as summaries of the original documents. These are directly linked in the text for comfort, in the event that extended details would be needed. This report tried to cover most aspects of the FAIR landscape of initiatives and organizations, therefore a wide audience can benefit from it. However, since developments and publications in this topic are produced continuously and rapidly, this report is not exhaustive and some aspects might be missing. In that case, comments are welcome for an incorporation in a later update.

Figure 1: Network of the FAIR projects and initiatives in Europe and transnational partners. Faced with the multiplication of FAIR related activities, this network aims at bringing more clarity and visualize the connections between these activities.

1- FAIR initiatives that create a framework for operations (umbrella organizations)

a. GO FAIR

i. Presentation

Global and Open FAIR (Figure 1) is a bottom-up, stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative. It provides a scaffold for the implementation of the FAIR data principles (Figure 1).

Individuals, institutions and organizations join their efforts through implementation networks (IN - see corresponding section below) that are active in three domains:

- go change: focus on the priorities, policies and incentives needed for a societal change in academic culture and for reaching higher amounts of FAIRness.
- go train: creation and coordination of a framework to train large number of competent and certified data stewards (see also chapter 4)
- go build: design, development and deployment of the technical standards, best practices and infrastructure components needed to enable the integration of data, tools, and computing capacities.

ii. Aims

- Support the creation and running of *GO FAIR* INs.
- Coordination between existing initiatives that target the development and implementation of FAIR Data & Services.
- Advocate for and support choices compliant with the FAIR guiding principles.
- Focus on early developments in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) with a global perspective.

iii. Implementation networks

The full list of the implementation networks is available [here](#), anyone (person, institution or network/organization) can join them. Some of the relevant ones for Biodata/GFBio's activities are:

- [BiodiFAIRse](#)
- Biodiversities (in preparation)
- [Chemistry](#)
- [Data stewardship competence centers](#): *GO UNI* for the German part; contacts: Monika Linne, linne@ub.uni-koeln.de, Patrick Helling, patrick.helling@uni-koeln.de-see also [chapter 4](#): Data Management Training - Data Stewardship Competence Centers.
- [FAIR microbiome](#)
- [FAIR StRePo: making Standards, Repositories, and Policies FAIR](#) (work with the Data Stewardship Wizard, DSW)
- [Food systems](#)
- [GAIA Data GlobAI Integrated EArth Data Implementation Network](#)
- [GeRDI Generic Research Data Infrastructures in Germany](#) (PANGAEA is partner)
- [Marine data centers](#) (AWI is partner)

b. FAIRSFAIR

i. Presentation

Fostering FAIR data Practice in Europe (Figure 1) is a three years project that started in March 2019, with 22 partners from 8 member states (6 core partners; project coordinator is DANS- Data Archiving and Network Services, Netherlands). Uni Bremen with the Marum/PANGAEA is one of the partners. The organization is embodied by five FAIR champions that are scientific experts with hands-on experience in the field of FAIR data: Alastair Dunning (Netherlands), Odile Hologne (France), Susanna-Assunta Sansone (UK), Andreas Rauber (Vienna), Tobias Weigel (Germany).

ii. Aims

- Develop and build a knowledge infrastructure, on quality data management, procedures, practices, standards, metrics and related matters, based on the FAIR principles.
- Provide a platform for identifying, coordinating and harmonizing the efforts of FAIR actors, to create a dialogue and find practical solutions for the day to day uptake of FAIR practices by the European research data providers and repositories, and for preventing the duplication of efforts.
- Enable and promote an interoperable EOSC and network of trusted repositories.
- Develop a capability maturity model towards FAIR certification (Figure 1)
- Set up a FAIR competence center for all communities and embed FAIR data education in university programs.

iii. Four areas of activities

FAIR data semantics, practices, and policies:

- surveillance of the landscape to identify overlaps, divergences and challenges and especially gaps in semantic interoperability, metadata and PIDs
- guidelines towards necessary changes in policy and practice at funder, repository and organizational levels
- improvement of the understanding of the current variety in FAIR data standards, metadata schemas, vocabularies, protocols and ontologies
- FAIR concept applied to data services (including software)

Certification of repositories:

- tools/methods to identify trustworthy repositories and to evaluate the FAIRness of individual datasets: "Capability maturity model towards FAIR certification" (see chapter 2e)
- support and guidance program for application to CoreTrustSeal (CTS)
- registry and network of 50+ trusted digital repositories with badges for end users

FAIR competence centers and FAIR data science professionalization:

(see *GO FAIR* implementation network above and chapter 4)

- tested framework for franchising data science schools with model courses and curricula (three annual workshops for higher education)

- train the trainer data science schools (five events per year)
- FAIR Competence Adoption booklet (three workshops on integrating FAIR data competences for universities + case studies)
- map of existing FAIR data training offers across education institutions (report FAIR data in European higher education and training for researchers)

Enabling a FAIR EOSC:

- ensure that the regulatory compliance to Rules of Participation to the EOSC will enable the rendering and maintaining of data, software and services following the FAIR principles
- the High Level Advisory committee will ensure that the outcomes are aligned and linked to other FAIR initiatives and in compliance with the EOSC RoP

2- Guidelines and Policies

Most of the incentives and concrete applications of guidelines and policies come from *FAIRsharing* (Figure 1), which shapes the overall adoption of the FAIR principles by the whole ecosystem, thanks to its multiple connections to other initiatives and organizations. *FAIRsharing's* three interlinked manually curated registries for standards, databases and data policies make it the cornerstone for the implementation of FAIR principles and one of the ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources (RIR).

a. Standards

i. SRAO & DRAO

FAIRsharing has developed and is maintaining the Subject Resource Application Ontology (SRAO) describing academic disciplines and the Domain Resource Application Ontology (DRAO) describing cross-discipline research domains. While the SRAO describes higher-level subject areas, the DRAO contains more specific domain terms and descriptors. The two application ontologies are built conjointly and all their respective classes stem from publicly-available ontologies and controlled vocabularies. Both these ontologies are used by the *FAIRsharing* curators to describe and classify standards, repositories and policies and are available for users to describe their own resources.

ii. Metadata for Machines (M4M)

Through a series of *workshops*, with *GO FAIR* as the umbrella organization and with inputs mainly from the *Research Data Alliance* (RDA), *FAIRsharing* has been defining a minimal set of machine-actionable metadata to be generated and provided by investigators to annotate their datasets, so that these become Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable by machines. These data/metadata standards should be quantitative and verifiable measures of the degrees by which digital objects meet the F, A, I, R guidelines. To promote the uptake of such practices and enable the investigators to create such metadata, the FAIR partners are creating openly accessible and unified templates in familiar, easy to use web forms, APIs, or other capture tools.

b. Databases and Repositories

i. FAIRification of data repositories

This work is done within *FAIRSF AIR*, work package 2: “FAIR practices: semantics, interoperability and services” which includes 70 participants from six communities, with a background as infrastructures, research and libraries. Their workshops and discussions led to the definition of features that data repositories should ideally exhibit to be FAIR themselves and, to expose and enhance the FAIRness of the digital objects they hold. These features are listed as a set of organizational and/or technical requirements in this [official FAIRSF AIR deliverable](#). *FAIRSF AIR* also offers a support program to guide data repositories wishing to receive the CTS certification. The overall aim is to harmonize the repositories to increase the discoverability and interoperability of the (meta)data they hold and in turn, foster closer alliances between data archives and researchers.

ii. Research Data Policies of Journals

With the overarching acknowledgement that research data need to be available together with the corresponding research article, there is an increasing number of scholarly journal policies that regulate this movement. However, these policies vary from journal to journal making it cumbersome for data stakeholders to understand what is expected from them, in order to comply to these policies. To answer the apparent need for a harmonization, a joint effort between *FAIRsharing*, publishers and the *RDA* led to the [publication](#) of a research data policy framework that defines fourteen features, distributed in six policy types (Figure 2).

These policy features and types are the result of the analysis, combination and harmonization of previously available research data policies, as well as discussions and reviews by the communities during *RDA* meetings. They form a comprehensive and flexible framework for journals to be adapted to their internal procedures and individual solutions. This work does not aim to provide a list of recommended data repositories nor criteria for their selection (see next section). Instead, it provides implementation guidance and template texts to be reused by journals, for the easy creation and consolidation of their own research data policies.

A wide adoption and promotion of these policies should reinforce the good practices of data management and sharing, as they simplify the understanding of expectations by research data stakeholders.

14 journal research data policy features arranged as 6 policy types (tiers)

	Policy 01	Policy 02	Policy 03	Policy 04	Policy 05	Policy 06
Definition of the research data	<input type="radio"/>					
Exceptions to policy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Embargoes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Supplementary materials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Data repositories	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Data citation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Data licensing	<input type="radio"/>					
Researcher/ author support	<input checked="" type="radio"/>					
Data availability statements		<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Data formats and standards				<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Mandatory data sharing (specific data types)				<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Mandatory data sharing (all papers)				<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Peer review of data				<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Data Management Plans (DMPs)				<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Provide information

The text for the policy feature will be included in the policy template but it is clear that the feature will not be enforced and checked as part of the publishing or peer review process

Provide information and action

The text of the policy feature is included and makes clear where applicable that the feature will be checked and enforced in the publishing or peer-review process

Figure 2: The journal research data policy features and their distribution in the policy types (extracted from the original RDA publication) As the number of the policy type increases, its stringency and the amount of features to comply to also increase.

iii. Data Repository Selection Criteria

A collaborative effort between *FAIRsharing*, *Datacite* and several scholarly publishers resulted in the release of a [Memorandum of Understanding](#), which proposes a set of criteria for the identification and selection of data repositories, that publishers will endorse and recommend to their authors as they submit their studies for publication (Figure 1). While several other organizations have previously defined lists of criteria to evaluate data repositories (CTS, TRUST principles, ELIXIR Core Data Resources (CDR) and Deposition Databases (EDD)- see next section), this initiative focuses on repositories that only accept submissions of user-generated data without professional subsequent curation, and it does not have an aim of certification. Alternatively, its aims are to guide journals in providing consistent recommendations on the one side, and to inform data repository managers of the features that are important for publishers, on the other side. The

criteria and their corresponding definitions ([here](#)) are classified according to two levels of importance: essential and desirable. The compliance with “essential criteria” is necessary in order to be recommended by publishers, whereas “desirable criteria” are, for now, considered as best practice and not widespread enough to be practically used as filters. In its collection of repositories, FAIRsharing currently uses these criteria and their corresponding values for filtering and curation.

iv. FAIR vs CoreTrustSeal vs ELIXIR Core Data Resources

There are several sources of endorsement that fall within three categories: formal certification (CTS), rules of engagement and lists of criteria (TRUST principles, CDRs and EDD) and general service quality requirements from local IT management. The tables presented hereafter were created for this present report using two ELIXIR webinars held in 2019:

- [ELIXIR resources - CoreTrustSeal Touchpoints](#) which compares the CDRs criteria with those of the CTS and then, the CDR criteria with the FAIR principles.
- [Trustworthy data repositories in the Life Sciences](#) which presents the CTS certification and its relation to the FAIR principles.

The interpretation of the FAIR principles, the CTS criteria and the CDR criteria may differ between the authors of the two webinars referenced above, leading to some approximative correspondence in the tables below. While the table 1A shows how the CTS and CDRs relate to the FAIR principles, the table 1B shows how some CTS and CDR “orphan criteria”, without a FAIR principle parent, can relate to each other.

FAIR	EDDRs - EDDs	CTS
F1 (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier	3d identifier use: does the resource provide persistent & unique identifiers?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • offer persistent identifiers (F1 & F3) • recommended data citations (F1) • searchable metadata catalogue to appropriate standards (F2, F3) • search facilities, inclusion in disciplinary or generic registries of resources (F4)
F2 Data are described with rich metadata	1d staff effort: number of FTE per year for the past 2-3 years (curators; bioinformaticians, technical staff) 3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data?	
F3 (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	3f(i) data availability - data sharing services: list services through which data is shared	
F4 Metadata specify the data identifier	3a identifier use: does the resource provide persistent & unique identifiers? 3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data?	
A1 (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	3a identifier use: does the resource provide persistent & unique identifiers? 3f(i) data availability - data sharing services: list services through which data is shared 3f(ii) data availability - data sharing formats: list formats for available data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • facilitate machine harvesting of the metadata (A1) • uses international and/or community standards (A1.1) • searchable metadata catalogue to appropriate standards (A1 & A1.1) • technical infrastructure: protection of facility, data, products services, users (A1.2) • data managed in compliance with discipline and ethical norms (A1.2) • responsibility for long-term preservation (A2)
A1.1 The protocol is open, free and universally implementable	3f(i) data availability - data sharing services: list services through which data is shared 4b open science: does the resource have a legal framework that supports open science?	
A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	4b open science: does the resource have a legal framework that supports open science? 4c privacy policy: does the resource have a publicly available privacy policy in which security around personal data and cookies are described?	
A2 Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	4e sustainable support and funding: demonstrate the past and future funding and/or other commitments that support the resource by the host institution and/or other entities	
I1 (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	2d dependency of other resources: do other resources have a dependency on the resource described here to provide that service? 3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data? 3f(ii) data availability - data sharing formats: list formats for available data	
I2 (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data?	
I3 (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	2d dependency of other resources: do other resources have a dependency on the resource described here to provide that service? 3e links to documentation of provenance: does the resource link to the scientific literature for provenance of facts or biological context?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • metadata required when the data are provided (I1) • formats used by the designated community (I1) • measures and plans for the possible evolution and migration of formats (I2) • ensure understandability of the data (I2) • ability to comment on, and/or rate data and metadata (I3) • provide citations to related works or links to citation indices (I3)
R1 (Meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	1d staff effort: number of FTE per year for the past 2-3 years (curators; bioinformaticians, technical staff) 3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data?	
R1.1 (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	4b open science: does the resource have a legal framework that supports open science?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • integrity and authenticity of the data (R1) • documentation of the completeness of the data and metadata (R1) • links to metadata and to other datasets (R1) • provenance data and related audit trails (R1.2) • maintains licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance (R1.1) • defined data and metadata: ensure relevance and understandability for users (R1.3) • technical data and metadata quality and assessment of adherence to schema (R1.3)
R1.2 (Meta)data are associated with their provenance	2d dependency of other resources: do other resources have a dependency on the resource described here to provide that service? 3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data? 3e links to documentation of provenance: does the resource link to the scientific literature for provenance of facts or biological context?	
R1.3 (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	3d use of standards: which community-recognised standards are used for the (meta)data?	

Table 1A: Correspondence of the CDR and CTS criteria to the FAIR principles.

ECDRs - EDDs		CTS
1a	archives vs knowledge bases: is the resource archival or a knowledge base?	R7 guarantee the integrity and authenticity of the data R10 long-term preservation in a planned and documented way R11 expertise to address technical data and metadata quality and ensure sufficient
1b	scope statement: describe the scientific coverage and comprehensiveness of the resource	R1 explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain
1c	international dimension: does the resource have a global footprint?	
2a	overall usage: what is the usage of the resource for the past 2-3 years?	
2b	potential usage: what is the estimated size of the global potential user community?	
2c	usage in research as measured through citation in the literature	
3b	data throughput: number of entries, records processed, genomes assembled per year, for the past 2-3 years	
3c	technical performance: percentage availability per month for key pages over the last 12 months, response time of said key pages	R15 repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides and its designated community
3g	customer service: helpdesk, user feedback, training activities	R16 the technical infrastructure of the repository provides protection of the facility and its data, products, services and users
4a	scientific advisory board: does the resource have one?	R6 the repository adopts mechanism(s) to secure ongoing expert guidance and feedback (in-house, external)
4d	ethics policy: does the resource have an ethics policy that complies with all relevant international standards and best practices?	R4 the repository ensures, that data are created, curated, accessed and used in compliance with disciplinary and ethical norms
5a	counterfactual analysis: what would be the impact on the scientific community if the resource had not existed, or were to disappear and not be replaced? Is the resource globally unique? What would the impact on other dependent resources be?	
5b	accelerating science: how does the resource accelerate science? Does the resource set standards, promote reuse of data or software, promote research efficiency?	
5c	translational data: are there 'translational' figure familiar to the audience that will help them grasp the core nature of the resource?	

Table 1B: Correspondence of the CDRs and CTS criteria not covered by the FAIR principles

c. FAIRness assessment

i. FAIRassist - census of assessment frameworks

FAIRassist is one of *FAIRsharing* directories (Figure 1). It lists and describes ten FAIRness assessment frameworks for datasets, developed by various organizations, each having their own interpretations of the FAIR principles. These resources measure the FAIRness of datasets by means of manual questionnaires or checklists, or else by automatic tests, which all aim to help data stakeholders understand and achieve greater levels of FAIRness. Their output is generally a FAIRness indicator or a score, with recommendations on how to improve it. A short description of each evaluators can be found in the Figure 1 and in the *FAIRsharing* table listing the full respective characteristics. A complementary representation of this inventory can be found in the *FAIRSFAR* report M2.7 - Annex B.

ii. FAIR Data Maturity Model

The *RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group* is composed of stakeholders from different scientific and research disciplines, from the industry and public sectors, all active in the field of FAIR principles, some also involved in the *GO FAIR* and/or *FAIRSFAR* initiatives. This joint effort focuses on core assessment criteria and methodologies, for evaluating the uptake and implementation of the FAIR principles.

Based on publicly available documentation and an online survey, the group firstly compared twelve transnational existing FAIRness assessment frameworks (some not mentioned in the *FAIRassist* registry- see above). They mapped each framework's respective sets of questions/answers to each FAIR principle. This analysis allows users to understand what is being evaluated and how it has been measured, depending on the respective interpretations of the FAIR principles by the owners of these frameworks.

This full [comparative analysis](#) showed the need for a normalization of the features and methodologies these assessments frameworks display. Hence, the group used it as well as several consultations and testing in the community to identify a set of common core indicators. They decomposed the original FAIR principles article and used subsequent clarifying articles and their *GO-FAIR* interpretations to define indicators and their target (data or metadata) and to provide example of possible solutions for reaching higher levels of FAIRness. Based on these indicators, the group created a generic a community-scalable [self assessment model](#) for measuring the maturity level of digital objects (datasets) (Figure 3). This model is not meant to be used as another evaluator. It is meant to identify "what needs to be measured to assess the FAIRness of a digital object".

Firstly, each core indicator gets assigned a priority (essential > important > useful) and a corresponding level of compliance from 0 to 4 (Figure 3, bottom half). Guidance and indications on the possible steps to take for achieving further compliance are provided in the document. This methodology allows the measure of progress.

A second and stricter methodology relies on a binary measure of pass/fail (Figure 3, right side). Only indicators with a level of compliance of 4 are a "pass", whereas indicators with levels of compliance of 0 to 3 are a "fail". The amount of "pass" for each priority (essential, important, useful) within each FAIR area (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) is counted. This count gives a FAIRness score between 0 and 5. For instance, a digital object would have a low score in the Accessible area if all essential indicators had a compliance level below 4, even if the important and useful indicators all had a level of compliance of 4.

A comprehensive representation of this FAIR Data Maturity Model illustrated by an example is shown in Figure 3. The combined methodologies thus creates a mechanism for assigning maturity levels of digital objects.

This [FAIR Data Maturity Model](#) was published and adopted as an official *RDA recommendation* in May 2020 and is intended as guidelines to assist owners of assessment methodologies in the implementation of their tools, to establish a common ground, improve their interoperability and in turn, so that the interpretation by users is eased. Each thematic community can adapt the model to their specific needs and expectations, and can use it before the data production/collection (during the Data Management Plan production) to set FAIRness levels to reach, or afterwards to test the achieved level.

Figure 3: Concept used for the measure of FAIRness of digital objects in the RDA Maturity model.

The graphs are the results of a model analysis extracted from the RDA report. The codes on the radar charts refer to the indicators codes. While the first approach (vertical) allows to observe the progress of a digital object's FAIRness, the stricter approach (horizontal) establishes a minimum of FAIRness to reach and allows the visualization of the compliance of a digital object to the most important indicators.

iii. FAIRness assessment of services

While the FAIR principles initially targeted datasets (see all of the above) rather than the services acting on them, the construction of a FAIR ecosystem also relies on FAIR services to create and keep these data FAIR. Several initiatives are currently investigating ways to extend these principles to data services, such as FAIRSFair and the RDA, among others. A series of three workshops led to the establishment of a set of [initial recommendations for services](#) to support the implementation of the FAIR principles. These recommendations cover: the certification of services, the essential infrastructure components, the stewardship of the data, the costs and rewards, the collaboration and support, and finally the data management. They were assigned priority scores which varied among the stakeholder groups and were later on transformed into actions that service providers can take to enable these recommendations. As a complement to and a further step of this work, the FAIRSFair work package 2: "FAIR practices: semantics, interoperability and services" reviewed the assessment frameworks presented in FAIRAssist (see chapter 2c-i) which target datasets, together with three services as use cases in this [preliminary study](#). Using these resources, the group plans to build and extend its

initial assessment framework targeting services for October 2020. The delivery of the final version is expected at the end of the *FAIRSFair* project, in 2022. Therefore, the group is actively looking for input and feedback on their work and calling for the participation of data services in the creation of this assessment tool.

d. Software (FAIRsoftware)

The ELIXIR-NL node, through the Netherlands eScience Center and the DANS generated [five recommendations](#) for the design of FAIR software:

#1: use a publicly accessible repository with version control

#2: add a license

#3: register your code in a community registry

#4: enable citation of the software

#5: use a software quality checklist

For each of these recommendations, definitions and help to choose the tools and resources to fulfill it are provided.

e. Biomedical Data

The initiative *FAIRplus*, managed by ELIXIR and Janssen (pharmaceutical company) is developing tools and guidelines for 'FAIRifying' pharmaceutical and health data. These tools and guidelines collected in a '[cookbook](#)' will be used on selected Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) project databases as use cases. The FAIRifying process follows eleven steps described in the Figure 4. In later stages of the project, trainings for data handlers (academia, SMEs, pharmaceutical) will be delivered to change the data management culture in the biomedical sciences.

*Figure 4: Steps for the FAIRification of datasets in IMIs
Illustration extracted from Carol Goble's presentation at the
ELIXIR SME forum 29th-30th of January 2020.*

3- Research Data Management (RDM) toolkits

a. GO FAIR

The *GO-FAIR* initiative published a "[first aid kit](#)" list of resources to guide researchers in organizing their data. It presents indications regarding where to find appropriate data repositories and RDM support, a selection of tools for RDM plans, information about persistent identifiers and licenses. Its comprehensiveness is quite limited as its purpose is solely to provide first guidance.

b. CONVERGE

CONVERGE is the ELIXIR project that builds a distributed research data management framework across Europe, based on local infrastructures and investments. As the practices,

service offers and gaps vary from national nodes to another, *CONVERGE* seeks to harmonize, align and standardize these national portfolios, in order to build FAIR data from the root and propose an ELIXIR-wide agreement on (meta)data standards, data management and archive. The project started in February 2020 and will run for 36 months, involving 29 research institutes from 22 countries. At its center lies a common [research data management toolkit](#) which is informed by an expert network, the national tools and trainings as well as demonstrator projects.

The expert network itself is made of two interwoven ones, each corresponding to an intranet ELIXIR group. The national data management coordinators network (data-management-coordinators@elixir-europe.org) sits at the core and the group is restricted to these members only. They hold an open monthly teleconference every last Monday of the month at 13:00 CEST/CET. The network of local experts and their connected interest group (data-management-experts@elixir-europe.org) sit at the periphery and is largely open; in fact self sign-up is strongly encouraged. The German representative is Ulrike Wittig, who is looking for collaborators to join her in this task.

The national tools are integrated within a common toolkit centered on the ELIXIR Data Stewardship Wizard (*DSW*), *FAIRDOM* (ELIXIR-DE and Hub), the Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (*NeLS*) and the CDRs and EDD (Figure 5).

The DSW is developed by ELIXIR-NL and ELIXIR-CZ and is informed by the policies and standards resulting from FAIR initiatives presented earlier in this report. It is an open service web-based toolkit knowledge model that can also be hosted locally. It consists of six parts, each encompassing questions about specific stages in the research data life cycle. Questions and answers are enriched with metrics that indicate to the user the level of FAIRness and openness of the data and the compliance to good data management practices. The hundred of questions were designed to reflect an “in-person interaction” with a data steward, with the succession of questions dependent on the answers previously given by the user. This interactive aspect distinguishes the DSW from other online data management planners. In case of issues or questions, relevant experts and data management resources are indicated to the users. The output of the questionnaire is an automatically generated textual and editable Data Management Plan (DMP) in intelligible English sentences. This combination of digital services with guidance (multimedia content, hints, links to external resources) and “in person” support is helping researchers at every stage of the data life cycle, from the planning of experiments to the storage of data and metadata, and it shows them the extent of good data management practices. The DSW will soon integrate the [DMPonline](#) web-based tool, developed by the Digital Curation Centre of the university of Edinburgh (DCC), which includes customizable DMP templates from multiple organization for specific funders. As a result, the DSW can also be used by data stewards as a checklist for the creation of DMPs, by data management experts to have a window to the scientists of their community, and by domain-specific funders and institutes to offer reusable calibrated templates.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the toolkit developed within ELIXIR CONVERGE. Figure from R. Pergl's presentation at the ELIXIR All-Hands in June 2020. This workflow maps the current available tools, services and resources in the CONVERGE common toolkit on the data life cycle.

While the DSW guides scientists through the design of the DMPs, *FAIRDOM* provides the software necessary to realize them and implement the data management best practices (Figure 6). It relies on the *SEEK* platform to give flexible access to datasets, models, simulations, processes and outcomes while preserving the associations between them. In *SEEK*, the ISA (Investigation, Study, Assay) format structure makes it easy to organize, compare, combine different datasets and to import/export data from other sources. Aside this data catalogue, *FAIRDOM* incorporates the *Rightfield* tool for the automatic embedding of ontology terms to Excel spreadsheets. This enables the creation of semantically enriched templates to be reused and shared by scientists to collect and annotate their data without having an understanding of the ontologies behind the templates. The annotation of the spreadsheets' content can be indexed and searched also through *Rightfield*. *OpenBIS* is used to further facilitate the collection of data and metadata associated with biological experiments. This versatile and scalable system supports the data workflows from the initial measurements (via microscopes, mass spectrometers or DNA sequencers) to the publication of the results, through the integration, sharing and connection to other data processing pipelines. In addition, the platform includes the *JWS Online* (JSON Web Signature) tool for the construction, modification, simulation and storage of SBML (System Biology Markup Language) models. *FAIRDOM* is connected to the *NeLS* through the *SEEK* platform. The Norwegian bioinformatics resource provides the infrastructure for the storage, processing and analysis

of data, particularly high-throughput sequencing. It also hosts the Galaxy web server and is a submission broker for the ENA since Spring 2020.

The ELIXIR *CONVERGE* common toolkit is completed by the CDRs and EDDs, as recommended data resources of fundamental importance for the life-science community and as recommended long term storage of experimental data.

Figure 6: The CONVERGE common toolkit.

Scheme from R. Pergl's ELIXIR All-Hands presentation, which shows how all national capacities in data management "converge" into a single catalogue.

As the actors of *CONVERGE* seek to expand this common toolkit to include a larger array of national tools, other national data management systems and data submission brokers such as [COPO](#), [e!DAL](#) or [GFBio](#) are particularly relevant. This comprehensive catalogue of already available tools allows/will allow scientists to select and combine them to create their own tailored data management workflows following the guidance of data stewards and/or the DSW.

Making and keeping the data FAIR would not be complete without the instruction of all data stakeholders: from trainers, researchers, data managers and data stewards to tool developers. Hence, the *CONVERGE* data management framework will be informed by demonstrator projects and national training offers and materials, in a feedback loop. In the *WP2: Training and Capacity building*, led by Celia van Gelder from the Dutch Techcenter for Life Sciences (DTL / ELIXIR-NE), the ELIXIR- training portal Tess is used as the repository to identify the current nationally available resources, potential overlaps, as well as gaps and needs. This [excel document](#) is the output of the group's analysis and they are currently studying the possibility of a certification for Data Stewardship training. This catalogue will be the basis for the establishment of a learning path for "Data Stewardship, Management and Analysis for the Life Sciences" during the Biohackathon 2020. The outcomes of this project also coordinated by Celia van Gelder, should be implemented in 2021-2022.

4- Data Management Training

a. ELIXIR-NL

The prominent role of the Netherlands node in the field of data management training is the result of a [project](#) held between 2018 and 2019, funded by the Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) and led by the DTL (Celia van Gelder) and the University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG-Salome Scholtens). This project aimed at professionalizing the Data Steward role in the life sciences by agreeing on knowledge, skills and competencies required from data stewards, as well as describing the job consistently within the various life sciences (see [poster](#)). These requirements, guided by the FAIR principles, were translated into concrete learning objectives around which education lines and training materials can be developed. They have recently received further funding for their follow-up project, from the Nationaal Programma Open Science in the Netherlands (NPOS F project). The [elevator pitch](#) and the corresponding [poster](#) were presented at the ISMB (International Conference on Intelligent Systems for Molecular Biology) conference this July 2020.

At the same time, the DTL/ELIXIR-NE node has established an open transnational [interest group](#) led by Jasmin Böhmer and opened to all collaborators interested in data stewardship. It is intended as a community hub where data stewards can informally exchange on their knowledge, useful tools, trainings, “tips and tricks” and experiences through their slack workspace and regular virtual meetings.

It is worth noting that some of the people involved in these initiatives are also involved in the following two recently established RDA Interest Groups: [Education and training on handling of research data](#) ; [Professionalizing data stewardship](#) (Figure 1)

b. TERMS4FAIRskills

In January 2019, the *FAIRsharing* project, together with the ELIXIR training platform, used the first outcomes of the DTL/UMCG project on that topic, to launch the [TERMS4FAIRskills](#) initiative with the objective to professionalize the roles of data stewards and data managers. *TERMS4FAIRskills* is creating and developing a terminology that will enable the consistent and accurate description of courses and their associated materials, to improve their discoverability and, in turn provide more tailored and specific curricula. Thus far, more than 255 terms have been described independently from their context, with their synonyms, hierarchy and relationships ([Slideshare](#) - [GitHub](#)). This controlled and structured vocabulary will not only make possible the design of FAIR assessments and stewardship curricula from the first stage on, but also to define precisely the knowledge, skills and abilities (KSAs) required for the profession of data steward. The initiative has identified three areas of activity, each with specific competence areas: institute and policy focused, project and research focused, data and e-infrastructure focused (Figure 7). The clear formalization of these areas of activity will aid both employers in writing job ads as well as potential candidates in writing relevant CVs in the research data management field as it is getting wider and wider.

Figure 7: The TERMS4FAIRskills matrices of data stewards roles

This figure ([10.5281/zenodo.3460552](https://zenodo.org/record/3460552)) shows the areas of activity for the three identified data steward roles as well as their respective responsibilities and tasks, their KSAs, and the learning objectives to be reached by trainings delivered in these areas. The KSAs fall within ranges of managerial, discipline-related, documentary and technical competences.

To prevent data management to be perceived as yet another administrative task, sensitization to data management related issues has to be done for all roles, involved at all stages of the data life-cycle. A recent [FAIRSF AIR workshop](#) (June 2020) pointed out the need for the including data management skills in higher education programs from Bachelor levels onwards as well as further trainings of researchers. Some initiatives are getting closer to universities and research performing institutions to raise awareness, provide support and disseminate these data skills.

c. Data Stewardship Competence Centers

GO-FAIR and FAIRSF AIR have joined their efforts to set up local data stewardship competence centers (DSCC) at national levels. These are expertise groups who collaborate with researchers at their own institutions and universities, to promote and consolidate good data management practices. All the local DSCCs belong to the dedicated GO-FAIR Implementation Network, which allows the pragmatic cooperation, the exchange and alignment of protocols, standards, formats and terminology to avoid the duplication of efforts.

In fact, the mission of the FAIRSF AIR WP7: “Data Science and Professionalization”, is to coordinate, systematize and accelerate the pedagogy and availability of trainings for data skills, data sciences and data stewardship. Through the development of education and training materials within a larger data competence framework, it seeks to embed FAIR data education in university programs and doctoral trainings. In parallel, following the [CODATA/RDA schools models](#) of a two weeks curriculum, the WP6: “Competence Centers” will deliver “train the trainer” courses to early career researchers and trainers, to propagate

foundational data science skills in Europe. Within *CONVERGE*, Celia van Gelden is in charge of creating a “train the trainer” working group. Combined together, these two *FAIRSFair* work packages will look at ways to include some of these training modules in core university programs and at the possibility of formal accreditation of these modules. The German DSCC is called *GO UNI* and is located in Köln. A virtual kick Off meeting of this DSCC has been planned for the 8th of October, by the coordinators Patrick Helling and Monika Linne. This founding meeting will identify competencies and needs in terms of skills, requirements and services for Data Stewardship Competence Centers. The registration can be done [here](#). Finally, in de.NBI, a recent overview of the trainings in data management has been presented in the paper *in prep.* by SIG4: “Interoperability and Data Management”.

Combining these different strategies with the ELIXIR infrastructure, should fix the current lack of homogeneity and centralization that are needed to foster a culture more focused on creating and keeping data FAIR, and to answer the incentives from funders and institutions.

Final remarks

The FAIR principles were never intended as an absolute aim to reach, but rather as guidance in discussions among different science communities, in particular the life sciences, so that they would agree on standards and common practices as well as on services to realize them, with the long term goal of better supporting the creation and subsequent stewardship of harmonized and reproducible research data. Hence, FAIRness is actionable, dynamic, incremental and requires long-term sustainable investments by all data stakeholders. This dynamism is reflected in the landscape and variety of regular outputs on the FAIR topic. This non-exhaustive report tried to bring some clarity in those, to provide contacts as well as “places to go to”, in particular for data management, and finally to bring awareness to its audience on the different opportunities for involvement and the developments that could impact/help them.

List of most resources used for this report

GO FAIR:

- [Homepage](#)
- [Implementation Networks](#)
- [GO FAIR Metadata for Machines \(M4M\)](#)
- [GO FAIR DSCC](#)
- [GO FAIR RDM starter toolkit](#)

FAIRSFAIR

- [Homepage](#)
- [FAIRSFAIR deliverables](#)
 - [Set of FAIR data repositories features](#)
 - [FAIRSFAIR assessment of services](#)
 - [Annex B of M2.7 Assessment Report of FAIRness of Services: Inventory of FAIRness assessment evaluators](#)
 - [Recommendations for Services in a FAIR data ecosystem](#)

FAIRsharing

- [Homepage](#)
- [FAIRassist: inventory of the data FAIRness assessment frameworks](#)
- [FAIRsharing SRAO](#)
- [FAIRsharing DRAO](#)
- [Memorandum of Understanding FAIRsharing, Datacite and publisher: set of criteria for the identification and selection of data repositories](#)
- [Data repository selection - criteria that matter](#)

FAIRplus

- [Homepage](#)
- [FAIRplus summary](#)
- [FAIRplus cookbook](#)

RDA - Interest and working groups:

- [Education and training on handling of research data](#)
- [Professionalizing data stewardship](#)
- [Data policy standardization and implementation](#)
 - [Research Data Policy Framework for All Journals and Publishers](#)
- [FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group](#)
 - [Comparative analysis FAIRness assessment frameworks](#)
 - [Official RDA recommendation](#)
 - [Maturity model](#)

ELIXIR

- [ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources](#)
- [webinar ELIXIR resources and CoreTrustSeal](#)
- [webinar CTS and the FAIR principles](#)

CONVERGE

- [Toolkit](#)
- [DSW](#)
- [DMP online tool](#)
- [FAIRDOM](#)
- [SEEK platform](#)
- [Rightfield](#)
- [OpenBIS](#)
- [JWS Online](#)

Data steward professionalization

- [NPOS F project](#)
 - [initial project](#)
 - [elevator pitch](#) and corresponding [poster](#)
- [DTL data stewards interest group](#)
- [Data stewards function landscape and its stakeholders](#)
- [Terms4FAIRskills](#)
 - [homepage](#)
 - [Slideshare](#) presentation of the project
 - [GitHub](#)